
Post Auricular Flaps in Helical Rim Defect

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ABSTRACT

Human ear is a complicated structure with closely adherent anterior skin. Choosing the best technique for its repair is a challenge. The advantage and disadvantage of each procedure is to be cautiously and judiciously weighed, although much depends on the operating surgeon's experience. An assessment of utility of simple post-auricular flap for correcting post traumatic ear rim defect of varying sizes was done in this study. This flap provided excellent result in 22 patients except one showing minimal superficial necrosis. The post auricular flap can cover helical rim defect of varying size with good result and minimal complication rate due to loose post auricular skin, similar texture, matching colour, rich blood supply and proximity to the defect.

KEY WORDS: ear, helical rim defect, post auricular flap

INTRODUCTION:

Restoration of anatomical structure to its original shape and position is one of the most important objective in reconstructive surgery. The complicated anatomy of Ear and its closely adherent anterior skin makes it difficult to choose the best repair technique for a given defect since various factors play their part in decision making including the pros and cons of each procedure and the experience of operating surgeon. Successful reconstruction of ear helical rim defect can be accomplished using post auricular tissue that recreate the anatomy with skin of satisfactory texture and colour. The most frequent deformity of helical rim occurs in facial burn, trauma, excision of tumour or harvesting of large composite graft. The post auricular skin flap is devised primarily for isolated defect of the helix. It can be used to reconstruct the entire helix or a portion. This two stage procedure can be performed under general anaesthesia or local anaesthesia (GA/LA). A post auricular flap can restore the sharp delineation of the helix. The post auricular skin flap is not used when the ear framework is of alloplastic material.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Twenty two patients of post traumatic helical rim defect were admitted and surgically treated in Department of Plastics Surgery, SMS Medical College, Jaipur (India) during January to December 2014. Informed consent was obtained prior to surgery. Demographic characteristics include age, gender and aetiology were documented. Patients were followed up regularly for three months and result were documented.

SURGICAL TECHNIQUE:

The surgeries were performed under GA/LA. The defect margin of the helical rim was denuded by excision of the scar margin. Thereafter, anterior margin of the post auricular incision was approximated to the posterior edge of the denuded helical defect. The incised mastoid skin flap was undermined for a distant of about 3 cm. Its anterior free margin easily covered the margin of the auricle. The upper and lower corner of the flap were sutured in to the open incision along the margin of the defect. The second stage was performed 3 week later. The necessary width of the flap was estimated and the flap was cut free from the mastoid. The procedure was modified according to the requirement of each patient.

Table 1: The post auricular flap provided good result in our 22 patients except in one patient showing minimal superficial necrosis.

S.N.	Age	Sex	Cause	Site of The Defect	Size Of Helical Rim Defect In Cm	Complication
1	14	M	Trauma	Upper third	3.0	Nil
2	33	m	Trauma	Upper third	2.7	Nil
3	54	M	Trauma	Upper third+Middle third	3.8	Nil
4	36	F	Trauma	Upper third+Middle third	3.6	Nil
5	23	M	Trauma	Upper third+Middle third	3.9	Nil
6	27	M	Trauma	Upper third	3.1	Nil
7	17	F	Trauma	Middle third	3.6	Nil
8	28	M	Trauma	Upper third+Middle third	4.1	Nil
9	31	M	Trauma	Middle third	3.6	Nil
10	24	M	Trauma	Upper third+Middle third	3.9	Nil
11	29	F	Trauma	Upper third+Middle third	2.9	Nil
12	22	M	Trauma	Upper third+Middle third	3.5	Nil
13	24	M	Trauma	Middle third	2.7	Nil
14	26	M	Trauma	Middle third	3.6	Nil
15	35	M	Trauma	Upper third+Middle third +Lower third	4.2	SUPERFICIAL NECROSIS
16	31	F	Trauma	Upper third	3.8	Nil
17	26	F	Trauma	Upper third+Middle third	3.4	Nil
18	28	M	Trauma	Middle third +Lower third	4.1	Nil
19	15	M	Trauma	Upper third+Middle third	3.7	Nil
20	14	M	Trauma	Middle third+Lower third	2.9	Nil
21	21	M	Trauma	Middle third	3.4	Nil
22	16	F	Trauma	Upper third+Middle third	3.7	Nil

Cartilage was not used in any case. The donor sites were primary closed. No skin graft was used in any case. Most defects were of upper and middle third of the helical rim.

DISCUSSION:

Reconstruction of the post-traumatic partial defect of ear, without reducing the size and without altering the natural shape, is a challenge. Primary closure was not an option since it could originate distortion of the auricular anatomy.

Given the cartilage exposition, a skin graft could be an unsafe option due to risk of necrosis. Second intention healing was a valid option and could simplify wound management. However, it can be a long process with serious risk of infection. Two stage local flap transposed from the postauricular or preauricular region are generally reserved for larger defect that include auricular periphery and require a second stage to remove the pedicle.^{1,2} If the helical defect is less than 1.5 cm in width and extends from the rim in to the scapha or triangular fossa, the defect can be converted into a wedge-shaped resection and can be closed

Figure 1: Showing gender wise case diffraction.

Figure 2: Showing no complication V/s complication.

Figure 3: Reconstruction of helical rim.

primarily.^[5] For defects between 1.5 and 2.5 cm in width, Antia-Buch helical chondrocutaneous advancement flaps allow for closure of the defect by creating further helical mobility.^[6] For isolated helical defects 2.5 cm and larger, the posterior auricular flap is a versatile, local workhorse flap. The post-auricular skin, considered a flap bank for ear reconstruction, offer safe vascularization and has similar colour and texture when compared with auricular skin.^[4] Therefore, this flap is relatively safe with favourable cosmetic result, a fact supported by our experience. Brown and cannon in 1946^[3] first used this postauricular area as a donor site for free skin and composite graft. Owens^[7] introduced in 1959 the concept of transposing the postauricular flap to the other side of the ear through a window in the cartilage with a buried de-epithelialized pedicle. In our experience, the pull through postauricular flap is a relatively simple flap to harvest and should be considered a feasible and desirable option in the reconstruction of defect of the post traumatic auricular defect.

CONCLUSION:

Postauricular flap can be used to reconstruct the entire helix or a portion. It is a two stage procedure. It uses the post auricular and mastoid skin which is a good match for the skin of the ear. A post auricular flap can restore the sharp delineation of the helix. For isolated helical defects 2.5 cm and larger, the posterior auricular flap is a versatile, local workhorse flap. The post auricular skin flap is not used when the ear framework is of alloplastic material.

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